

The Role of Fathers in Providing Nutrition Intake to Toddlers in Reducing Stunting in Bandung City

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Abstract:- Background: The prevalence of stunting in West Java is 29.2% or 2.7 million toddlers. The incidence of stunting in Indonesia is sufficient tall. If compared to income countries medium. Stunting incident according to Basic Health Research (Reseda's) in 2018 is 10.2% meanwhile prevalence of stunting in children toddlers 30.8% (Ministry of Health 2018). The number of children under five suffering from stunting (failed growing) in the city of Bandung experienced increase in 2020. From data from the Bandung City Health Office, numbers stunting toddlers reached 9,567 or 8.93 percent of 107,189 toddlers who have been measured (Lolan, Lau and Sinaga, 2022). **Method:** Research a This is study observational analytic with design get up cross sectional research. On research this, the variables studied are the husband and father's role in improvement of nutritional status. The chi square correlation test was used for analyzing relationship between independent and dependent variables. **Results:** Less roles support dad inside gift intake nutrition in stunting toddlers with mark the proportions are 61.9%, while of fathers are supportive gift intake nutrition in under five statuses normal 69%. On research This the P-value is 0.291 which means No There is meaningful father's role in stunting toddlers. **Conclusion:** The role of the father in family Not only affects the change in socioeconomic status family but also related tightly with father's involvement in parenting. Father's involvement in parenting includes aspects time, interaction, and attention to child. Father's involvement in parenting No just quantity more time for children *but quality the interaction also matters also matter basic. The role of a father in toddlers No lost importance with a mother in fact also matter.*

Keywords:- Father's Role, Intake Nutrition, Stunting.

I. INTRODUCTION

Stunting is caused by multi-dimensional factors, namely practice parenting that isn't good in the First 1000 Days Life (HPK) of children because not enough knowledge about health and nutrition before and during pregnancy, no get exclusive breastfeeding in children 0-24 months old, no accept Food Companion ASI (MP ASI), limited service health (incl services Ante Natal Care, Post Natal and learning early quality), lack access to food nutritious. Improve nutritional status public is an indicator second on the

goal of Sustainable Development or SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) both realized with trying endin starvation, reach resilience good food and nutrition, as well increase agricultural sustainability. The year 2030 is expected effort the has successful success in finishing various type problem-related nutrition with availability food with remove all form starving or malnutrition and guarantee access for everyone, especially the poor and people who are conditions in condition prone to be, nutritious and sufficient food (Lolan, Lau and Sinaga, 2022). A total of 10 (ten) villages spread across 8 (eight) districts in Bandung Regency became priority handling stunting, because sufficient was prevalence high. Each is Village Rancatungku (Pameungpeuk), Dampit, Narawita and Tanjungwangi (Cicalengka), Mekarlaksana (Cikancung), Babakan (Ciparay), Girimulya (Pacet), Cihawuk (Kertasari), Karangtunggal (Paseh) and Village Cibodas (Kec. Pasirjambu District) (Lolan and Sutriyawan, 2021). Indonesia included in a third country with prevalence the highest in the Southeast Asia / Southeast Asia (SEAR) region. The average prevalence of stunting under five in Indonesia in 2005-2017 was 36.4%. 3 more from a third (37%) of children under five in Indonesia experienced stunting in 2013 and its prevalence exceeding 40% in 15 of 33 Provinces. WHO target lower stunting rates in children not enough from 5 years namely 40% in 2025. In 2018, East Nusa Tenggara is 42.6%, West Sulawesi is 42% and Aceh is 35%. The prevalence of stunting in West Java is 29.2% or 2.7 million toddlers. The incidence of stunting in Indonesia is sufficient tall. If compared to income countries medium. Stunting incident according to Basic Health Research (Rikesdas) in 2018 is 10.2% meanwhile prevalence of stunting in children toddlers 30.8% (Ministry of Health, 2018) (Ministry of Health RI, 2018). The number of children under five suffering from stunting (failed growing) in the city of Bandung experienced increase in 2020. From data from the Bandung City Health Office, numbers stunting toddlers reached 9,567 or 8.93 percent of 107,189 toddlers who have been measured (Lolan, Lau and Sinaga, 2022)

II. METHOD

Study This is *observational analytic* with design get up study *cross sectional*. On research this, the variables studied are support husband and father's role in improvement of nutritional status toddler. Correlation test *chi square* used for analyzing relationship between independent and dependent variables. The sample used in study this father owns baby 6 months old until with 24 months.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Factor	Total (n=102)	Percent (%)
Nutritional Status		
stunt	63	61.8
Normal	39	38.2
Husband 's Role		
Less Support	66	64.7
Support	36	35.3

Table 1. Distribution Respondents

From the description in table 1 above can see that the average respondent has toddler status stunting nutrition by 63 with percentage by 61.8% and the average respondent is less support pattern foster in gift Eat nutritious by 66 respondents with percentage 64.7%.

Table 2. Risk Factors for Stunting in Toddlers

Factor	Nutritional Status						P-Value
	stunt		Normal		Total		
	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Less Support	39	61.9	27	38	63	100	0.291
Support	27	69.2	12	30.8	39	100	

Less role support dad inside gift intake nutrition in stunting toddlers with mark the proportions is 61.9%, while fathers are supportive gift intake nutrition in under five status normal nutrition 69%. On research This mark *P-value* 0.291 which means No There is meaningful relationship _ between father role with stunting incident in the city of Bandung. According to Effendy 2009, support family is attitude or action reception family to member his family, form support informational, support assessment, instrumental support, and support emotional. According to him, support family is very important Because family is the smallest unit in society and so reception care nursing. So from That family so role in determine method care needed by members _ sick family , if in family that’s one member his family some are experience problem health so system in family will affected (Lolan and Somantri, 2022) . So, support family is something form interpersonal relationships that include attitudes , actions and acceptance to member family , so member family feel anyone noticed (Lolan, Lau and Sinaga, 2022) . this describe that the behavior of the father in love love toddlers. Enough Good although fathers are rare parenting child her toddler because dad is busy in work. The role held by the father is not lost important from role one caring and nurturing mother _ child at home because father’s role is also important in form growth and development childlike development emotional in children. If a father gives love Darling fully to child so child will feel happy and feel comfortable when near with his father and better if a father is not giving attention and affection to his son, then child will feel sad and feeling No comfortable when together his father. Father's attitude is not affecting nutritional status toddler

because there is the most important factor affect nutritional status toddler that is food with good nutrition. Food with various substance much needed nutrition toddler for its growth and development. Toddler will grow optimally if intake eat it in amount sufficient, nutritious, and balanced (Aini et al, 2013).

Parental attitude specifically behavior health like fulfillment nutrition in children can cause Error perceptions and patterns care for toddlers. In study This attitude is parental attitude form evaluation on nutritional status child toddler, way gift food For child toddler , growth child toddler . (Lolan and Sutriyawan, 2021) explained that There is connection between attitude of people with incidence of stunting in toddlers. Parenting patterns in a manner No langs ung will affect nutritional status child. parenting manifested in several usual activities done by mother like practice gift Eat child, practice sanitation and care health son to be own impact big for health future child. Giving food that doesn't notice frequency delivery, quality nutrition and methods gift eat less right too would result failure growth.

This prove exists linkages between knowledge and attitudinal, attitude positive influenced by good knowledge. Study This in line with research conducted by (Harikatang et al. , 2020) . In study he said that more from half respondent own positive attitude namely 34 respondents (57.6%). Attitude possessed positive Mother No regardless from knowledge or information that has acquired, and the knowledge possessed Mother Good or in category tall so that matter the form attitude positive or evaluation good mother to stunting incident. According to Rahmayanti, Dewi and Fitriani, 2020) Attitude is reaction or still response closed from somebody to something stimulation or object , where attitude basically No can direct seen, however only can interpreted especially formerly from closed behavior . Attitude Not yet is something action or activity, will but form predisposition action something behavior and is pusher behavior somebody For Act However attitude positive just without supported other factors yet Of course ensure somebody For do something. Father's role in family Not only Affects change in socioeconomic status family and relates tightly to's involvement in parenting. Father's involvement in parenting includes aspects time, interaction, and attention to child. Father's involvement in parenting No just quantity more time for children but quality the interaction that is built is also matter basic. The role of a father in toddlers No lost importance with a mother in fulfillment nutrition. Dad works the same for regulate and control expenditure family. Father's involvement in parenting is father 's participation Keep going continuously in parenting pregnant child aspect frequency, initiative, and empowerment personal in dimensions physical, emotional, social, intellectual, and moral. Research This in line reluctantly research conducted by (Aritonang, Hastuti and Puspitawati, 2020) which states from test results show that father's involvement in parenting influential positive significant to development cognitive child 2-3 years old in the area prevalence of stunting. Findings the in line with study earlier also found that father's involvement in parenting own effect significant to cognitive children (Perales & Baxter, 2018)

IV. CONCLUSION

Factor risk stunting in toddlers is Education level, processing local eating, parental knowledge, role power health, support husband. most related factors with stunting are support husband. Support husband or family is one of the most influential factors with stunting incident p This because father's role in family No solely for look for or increase economy just tapis other than that dad has role important in parenting. Father's involvement in parenting covers aspect time, interaction, and attention to child can influential positive significant to development cognitive child 2-3 years old in the area prevalence of stunting.

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